

REDEFINING THE LIMITS OF CONCRETE BRIDGE CONSTRUCTION WITH NON-METALLIC REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The planned pedestrian crossing on Ludwigsburger Straße in Stuttgart is a challenging curved concrete bridge combining a mix of FRP reinforcement types. Spanning 34 m over two spans, the bridge utilizes a circular ring girder concept. Stiffening ribs of only 15 cm depth, placed at 2.4 m intervals, support a thin 10 cm deck slab. The structure comprises precast elements in a semi-integral design. The paper highlights the design process, scientific investigations, and validation of the load-bearing capacity by means of a 1:1 test on one rib. It addresses the feasibility of using straight GFRP bars in frame corners and their interaction with other materials.

KEYWORDS

CFRP grid; GFRP bar; integral bridge; ring girder; precast elements; fiber-optic sensors

INTRODUCTION

As part of the Hummelgraben landscape development concept, a bridge for pedestrians and cyclists is to be built in the Stuttgart district of Zuffenhausen on the northern city boundary as a path connection across Ludwigsburger Street. As part of the overall project, new regional and supra-regional bicycle connections are to be created and existing connections improved.

In order to ensure a seamless connection to the planned pathway, a curved shape was agreed upon in the early planning phases (Figure 1). By using non-metallic reinforcement in combination with high-strength concrete, the cross-sectional dimensions of the concrete structure, especially the visible edges of the slab and the prominent web ribs, can be kept to a minimum. Furthermore, additional sealing and protective asphalt or polymer layers avoided. The structural design office for this project (knippershelbig GmbH) has already recognized the potential of the construction method with non-metallic grid reinforcement, formerly called textile concrete, today often referred to as carbon concrete, and has successfully used it in bridge structures in cooperation with Institute of Structural Concrete (IMB) of RWTH Aachen University (Bielak et al., 2020; Helbig et al., 2016). Since the city of Stuttgart and the local civil engineering office as the construction authority were also able to gain experience with the innovative construction method with the reconstruction of the Rosenstein bridge II (Rettinger et al., 2020), they also advocated its use here in order to redefine the limits of concrete construction once again.

Figure 1: Rendering of the bridge design across the Ludwigsburger Street in Stuttgart
(Graphic: knippershelbig)

DESCRIPTION OF CONSTRUCTION

Geometry and design

The bridge structure is designed as a two-span slender bridge with curved ground plan and spans of 17.0 m each, a structural width of 4.40 m, and a structural height of 1.90 m. A clear bridge width of 3.20 m is selected, which is kept constant over the curved course. On the inside, the web wall with openings parametrically adapted to the internal forces forms the spatial boundary for the users. At the outer edge, an inwardly inclined filigree steel railing closes off the bridge space. The 16 radial ribs give the underside of the bridge a regular sharp-edged appearance. To achieve a clear height under the bridge of 4.70 m, earth ramps rise to the beginning of the abutment bodies. The cut-out circular ring is slightly spatially inclined so that the north-eastern abutment is lower, which gives the bridge a flowing dynamic.

The two spans of the superstructure will be precast and coupled together on site at the joints. To the abutment, a connection is made to the abutment wall and the cast-in-place concrete deck. The superstructure is supported on one point at the central support. The subsequent grouting at the joints in the center of the field and at the abutments forms a semi-integral structure.

Structural concept

To form an exceptionally slender and durable structure, the concrete superstructure is reinforced with non-metallic fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) bars and grids. Due to their high tensile strength, excellent corrosion resistance and, depending on the bar diameter, reduced concrete cover, the deck slab of the precast bridge elements, for example, can be realized with two-layer carbon fiber composite plastic (CFRP) grid reinforcement in the thickness of only 10 cm. The slab spans locally over the prominent radial ribs of width 15 cm arranged with 2.4 m spacing. These ribs are placed on the underside of the deck and on the outside of the rear wall and locally stiffen in the secondary load-bearing direction (Figure 2). The ribs are reinforced with preformed CFRP grids. To support the opening moment in the frame corner, each rib is equipped with glass fiber composite (GFRP) bars as the main reinforcement in vertical, horizontal and diagonal direction.

The principal load-bearing action across the two spans in the longitudinal direction of the bridge (ring direction) is provided by a main girder consisting of a web, bottom chord and top chord. The rear wall or side wall arranged at the inner edge acts as a web, the function of the bottom chord is assumed by the deck slab, and the top chord is formed by a thickened head of the rear wall, which is called hammer head because of its triangular cross-sectional shape. To transfer the torsional moments resulting from the eccentric support, the globally curved shape is used as a circular ring girder. The ribs transfer the torsional moment as a transverse moment into the chords.

The hammer head forms the tensile support for the reaction force acting radially outward, and the deck acts as a horizontal compression arch as support to transfer the lower reaction force acting radially inward. The hammer head contains an internal steel tendon without bond, which is

subsequently prestressed against the abutment walls. Due to the geometric shape of the hammer head, radially inward deflection forces are generated in the hammer head during prestressing, which wedge and prestress it against the abutments. This allows the tension arc of the circular ring girder to remain free of tensile stress. A predefined erection sequence is chosen to reduce the support moments and the resulting tensile forces in the hammer head. The inwardly inclined central column supports the compressive action in the arch by its horizontal force component.

The shear force resistance of the circular ring girder is disturbed by existing sight openings in the web. These rectangular-shaped openings therefore become smaller and smaller in line with the shear force towards the supports. Secondary moments from the resulting Vierendeel action are resisted with discrete vertical GFRP reinforcement bars.

The connections between the two precast elements to each other and to the abutments are provided with stainless steel reinforcement bars arranged centric in the slab and in the hammer head to form the semi-integral action. The resulting jointless design increases durability, reduces the need for maintenance, and improves appearance by preventing uncontrolled stains from runoff of rainwater.

The abutment members, to be constructed in cast-in-place concrete in advance, are founded on a top slab with drilled piles. Since these components were not subject to any requirement for visual slenderness, they were designed conventionally in reinforced concrete.

Figure 2: Bottom view of the bridge model with ribs and central support (Graphic: knippershelbig)

Materials for the superstructure

The reinforcement products used for the superstructure were chosen during structural design in cooperation between the designer and the expert. Figure 3 (a) shows the planar CFRP grid used in the slab and in the rear wall as planar reinforcement. It has a fiber cross-section of 3.62 mm² and 95 mm²/m, respectively, and achieves mean ultimate stresses of 3300 N/mm² and Young's moduli of 230,000 N/mm² in both grid directions (0° and 90°).

Preformed CFRP grids made of the same base material with a standard bending radius of 10 mm are planned in the webs and as edge reinforcement (Figure 3 (b)). All visible edges are provided with oversized chamfers (25 mm) to achieve an even slimmer appearance. This is taken into account in the bending radius of the edge-forming profiles (35 mm). The concentrated supplementary reinforcement of the webs and the Vierendeel girder of the rear wall is formed by straight GFRP bars of nominal diameters 16 mm and 20 mm, Figure 3 (c). The bars have a general approval for use in construction works in Germany for a limited application range, which is, however, exceeded here (Schöck Bauteile GmbH, 2019).

Figure 3: Non-metallic reinforcement for the bridge

According to the design, the concrete for the superstructure must reach European strength class C80/95, be as self-compacting as possible and comply with the regulations analogous to conventional reinforced and prestressed concrete construction (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V [DIN], 2008, 2021). According to this, a maximum aggregate size > 4 mm is required. There are no requirements for the concrete to protect the reinforcement against corrosion. For the directly exposed concrete surfaces, the exposure class XF4 applies. It is known from previous projects that sufficient frost and de-icing salt resistance of the concrete can be demonstrated experimentally (e.g. (Helbig et al., 2016)) if sufficiently high compressive strength cannot be achieved with the use of air-entraining agents to achieve the minimum air content according to Annex F in (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V [DIN], 2008). Alternatively, it was argued, e.g. for the bridge in (Bielak et al., 2021), that a high-strength concrete has properties analogous to an earth-moist concrete (according to (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V [DIN], 2008) $w/c \leq 0.4$) due to its low w/c ratio and is thus sufficiently resistant to frost and de-icing salt (see also (Dehn & Wiens, 2022)). The high-strength concretes developed within the Carbon-Concrete Composites (C³) project (Heiermann & Vollpracht, 2017) also exhibited sufficient frost and de-icing salt resistance, as confirmed experimentally. Since the final concrete formulation meeting the above-mentioned requirements is to be determined only by the executing company, a concrete with corresponding properties from a completed research project of the IMB of the RWTH was selected as an alternative for the necessary experimental component tests (see (Hegger & Heid, 2021) and concrete "C2" in (Heid, 2021)). This concrete has already been successfully used for very dense reinforcement arrangements of CFRP/GFRP grids and carbon tension bars in 60 mm thick face layers.

CONSTRUCTION WITH NON-METALLIC REINFORCEMENT OUTSIDE OF APPROVALS AND STANDARDS

Legal framework

The German model building code and the federal state building codes, in this case for the state of Baden-Württemberg in Germany (Land Baden-Württemberg, 2021), indicate paths for building with non-regulated products and construction methods for building structures. Transportation facilities and associated ancillary structures are exempt. The bridge over Ludwigsburger Street falls under the regulations of the Road Act of Baden-Württemberg (StrG, 2022/11. Mai 1992)], and the city of Stuttgart, as the public authority responsible for construction, is also responsible for all tasks related to the construction and maintenance of roads (Rettinger et al., 2020). Consequently, the local civil engineering office, as the road authority responsible for the city of Stuttgart, can itself grant approval in individual cases with project-related construction approval. The basis for this decision is, in addition to the involvement of an inspecting structural engineer, in general a technical statement by a suitable expert, which if necessary can also be combined with experimental investigations. However, this is not laid down by law in detail, but is left to the discretion of the approving authority. The local civil engineering office of the city of Stuttgart has experience with carbon concrete in bridge

construction from previous projects (Rettinger et al., 2020), but in the present case the complexity is even greater. Ultimately, the "road construction authorities are responsible for ensuring that their structures meet all the requirements of public safety and order", see § 9a in (StrG, 2022/11. Mai 1992). In the present case, the local civil engineering office therefore decided to obtain an expert opinion.

It is crucial for the quality of the final structure that clear regulations on certification, the manufacturer's declaration of conformity and on in-house and external monitoring are laid down in the approval notice. These accompany the actual expert assessment and are intended to ensure that the values and boundary conditions assumed in the structural analysis and expert opinion are in conformity with those in the final construction product. This is urgently required in view of the lack of regulations for the design of non-metallic reinforced concrete components and the lower tolerances required for components with greatly reduced dimensions. The regulations from (Land Baden-Württemberg, 2021) can be usefully transferred and, if necessary, supplemented for this purpose.

Proposed program of investigation

In the present project, the expert assessment of adequate load-bearing and deformation behavior is challenging for several reasons. A load test of the whole or one half of the superstructure, as was done at the time for the carbon concrete bridge in Albstadt-Ebingen (Helbig et al., 2016), is excluded for economic reasons and would also be technically extremely challenging. The structure only becomes functional through the global compression arch effect in conjunction with the prestressing, and this would be very complicated to reproduce in the test. Since the principal load transfer of the tension member made of steel strands and the concrete in compression can be verified with conventional methods and models of reinforced and prestressed concrete construction, the necessity for this was also not given from the point of view of those involved. The IMB of the RWTH, in cooperation with the local civil engineering office and the designer as well as the inspecting structural engineer, therefore proposed a mixed verification format consisting of small and medium experimental investigations (Table 1) and theoretical investigations as well as the use of existing results from approval and research projects. The core of the evaluation is the question of whether the nonlinear 3D finite element calculation model used by the designer and the simplified strut-and-tie model for the supporting ribs are able to adequately predict the force distribution in the reinforcement and concrete, the overall load-bearing behavior and the deformation behavior. For the comparison, a representative rib segment consisting of web, slab, back wall and hammer head was defined to be loaded to failure in a 1:1 full-scale test. This component functions as a frame corner with opening moment in the secondary support system of the bridge superstructure and is the critical element of the bridge from the point of view of the participants. The GFRP bars used as the main tensile reinforcement are anchored straight – in contrast to what is usual in reinforced concrete construction for frame corners – because corresponding preformed elements from the manufacturer are available, but are not approved by the building authorities and they are much less comprehensively characterized.

With the production of the ribbed element for the large-scale test, knowledge can be gained on the manufacturability of the reinforcement cage and the concreting capability. However, it is also clear that a single short-term test is not suitable for experimentally determining long-term deformations or for determining statistically significant test numbers for deriving characteristic resistances. Rather, it is a matter of a phenomenological investigation of failure initiation, failure mechanisms, stress distribution and cracking behavior.

Table 1: Overview of test program

Test Method	Purpose of investigation
Survey for initial approval	
Component test on frame corner	Manufacturability of the bridge, esp. concreting; Crack formation behavior; Crack widths in the frame corner; Anchorage behavior of the GFRP bars and CFRP grids; Effectiveness shear force reinforcement; Interaction grid and bar reinforcement
Preformed CFRP grid tensile tests	Tensile strength and modulus of elasticity in the straight part; Strength in the bend
Preformed CFRP grids bending tests (overlap)	Load capacity of the overlap of the shear reinforcement (U-profiles) in the web
(In-house) manufacturing control	
GRP bars tensile tests	Conformity check for tensile strength, modulus of elasticity
Plane CFRP grid tensile tests	Conformity check for tensile strength, modulus of elasticity
Preformed CFRP grid tensile tests	Conformity check for strength in the bend, modulus of elasticity, radius of bend

For the prediction of the flexural and shear resistance of the slab as well as for the verification of the anchorage or overlap, models in research are available that have meanwhile also found their way into the draft guideline "Concrete components with non-metallic reinforcement" of the German Committee for Reinforced Concrete adopted by the Subcommittee for Non-Metallic Reinforcement (Deutscher Ausschuss für Stahlbeton, 2022). These models are based on material characteristics determined by suitable (standardized) test methods. For planar reinforcement, extensive results from previous projects and manufacturers' data are available. For the preformed reinforcement, however, which has an essential load-bearing function in the web of the rib as shear force and splitting tensile reinforcement, there is a lack of sufficient resistance characteristics. The investigations in (Bielak, 2021) showed that significant reductions in strength and modulus of elasticity must be expected compared to the planar reinforcement material of the same reinforcement cross-section. The reasons for this are a lower parallelization of the fibers in the free part due to the different manufacturing process, the non-constant (linear) stress distribution over the fiber strand cross-section in the bend under tensile loading, and local stress concentrations in the anisotropic material in the bend. The characteristic values required for the calculation must therefore be determined experimentally in uniaxial tensile tests and in yarn pull-out test on the curved embedded element for the expert opinion. One particular detail of the bridge geometry also justified new flexural tests to characterize the lap joint of the grid reinforcement: Due to the haunching of the rib, the web reinforcement has to be composed of two U-connectors, since an (economical) fabrication of closed cages with haunches is not possible with the designated biaxial grid material. Closed haunch cages would also make the installation of the straight rebars considerably more difficult. Since the U-shaped reinforcement elements must be aligned orthogonally to the free edge, this results in an overlap joint rotated by 7.7° , the length of which is also limited by the available width of the base material. Whether such a joint - which is rather short - can provide sufficient load-bearing capacity without premature spalling had to be clarified. Finally, the strength of the preformed CFRP used in the models is obtained from the minimum of the values in the free length, the bend, and the overlap joint. The investigation program and the expert opinion based on it do not aim to verify the impacts (in particular temperature, effect of prestressing, shrinkage and creep) and the internal force calculation for the structure. These are subject to the regular structural engineering review. In the following, a part of the investigation program, the component test, is described in more detail.

COMPONENT TEST

Test concept and measurement technology

The frame corner element was designed on a 1:1 scale, and the geometry was only slightly simplified compared to the final bridge: for example, no edge upstand was provided below the railing, formwork edges were straightened for easier support, and the reinforcement in the slab was aligned orthogonally to the web. A width of 50 cm was chosen for the specimen, corresponding to the distance between two vertical openings in the back wall directly adjacent to each rib. This allows the monolithic load-bearing behaviour between the slab and the back wall as well as the secondary bending moments acting there to be recorded, and the crack formation or crack progression in the frame corner to be better estimated.

The decisive action for the frame corner is the full-area loading of the slab from dead weight and life-load, which is transferred to the rib element as a line load. Such loading is complex to simulate in terms of testing, which is why an equivalent substitute concentrated load was applied at a clear distance of 1.9 m from the rear wall (Figure 4). This distance results in a similar moment-shear ratio at the presumed critical point (distance d (effective depth) from the corner), and a sufficiently large shear span so that no direct compression strut occurs and a flexural shear or shear tension failure is prevented.

In the real structure, the ribs are supported at the bottom on the inner, horizontal compression arch, and they are held at the top by the curved tendon in the hammer head. This pair of forces results in local restraint. In the test, this system is approximated by horizontal support on a 1 m thick prestressed reaction wall with steel compression struts in the axis of the slab and tension rods in the axis of the hollow tube for the tendon. Vertical support is provided indirectly by arranging the back wall stubs projecting laterally over the web on steel rollers in their central plane. This form of “hanging” the specimen is of particular importance in order to simulate the stresses in the anchorage area of the principal reinforcement similar to those in the real structure. If the specimen had been directly supported on the underside of the web, compressive stress and direct load transfer would have resulted. The rotation point of the test specimen is thus located in the intersection axis of the slab and the back wall.

The load is applied by means of a manually controlled hydraulic pump (force-controlled), 5 kN/min was specified as the loading speed. As intended, unloading was planned after the calculated initial crack formation in the frame corner to assess the crack widths in serviceability limit state with subsequent reloading until failure.

Figure 4: Sketch of the test specimen with support and load point (Graphic: knippershelbig)

A core objective of the component test is to validate the models by comparing calculated with measured stresses, resistances, and observed failure modes. For this purpose, extensive internal and external measurement equipment was applied (Figure 5): Conventional displacement transducers measure the deformation under the load as well as in the supports to be capable of correcting rigid body displacements/rotations from the support deformation. Digital image correlation is used to track

crack initiation and crack growth in the web (2D) and in the slab and back wall in the frame corner (3D). Strain gauges (DMS) and fiber optic sensors (FOS) are applied to the main tensile reinforcement as internal measurement technology. This allows to record the strain (and stress) progression in the GFRP bars continuously, especially in the anchorage zone.

Figure 5: Measurement technology for the large-scale test (Graphic: IMB RWTH)

Production

The test specimen was manufactured by positive casting. This form of production corresponds to the production of the later precast bridge elements anticipated by the parties involved, similar to a so-called π -slab in a precast plant, i.e. with recessing of the ribs into a formwork floor. The reinforcement cage was assembled step by step, whereby special care was required around the contact points of the bar reinforcement in three spatial directions with applied measuring technology (Figure 6). The well-known problem of mutual insertion of grid-shaped reinforcements (e.g. (Bielak et al., 2019)) was solved here by using the same grid opening sizes and by removing the longitudinal fiber strands in the vertical part of the U-section inserted from above as the upper part of the shear force reinforcement in the web.

Figure 6: Finished reinforcement cage before closing the side formwork (Graphic: IMB RWTH)

Concrete casting was done in two steps so that the venting of the slab would not be hindered by a closed formwork cover and so that the top of the slab could have a smooth finish. An upstand of approx. 10 cm is intended to meet the requirement of water-tightness in the corner area in serviceability limit state, i.e. the construction joint should not lie exactly in the corner between the bridge deck and the rear wall, which will later serve for drainage in the longitudinal direction of the bridge. Whether the real bridge is also manufactured with a joint or monolithically depends on the

manufacturability with the concrete used, as well as the existing formwork and compaction system. Fabrication in two steps allows the inclined support of the rear wall against the hardened slab but is more time-consuming and may involve reworking in the construction joint area. Fabrication and testing with construction joint provides presumptive conservative resistances. In the first concreting step, the concrete was too stiff during placement (slump flow $t_{500} = 12.9$ s according to (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V [DIN], Dezember 2010)), and flow around the reinforcement was only partially successful. The concreting section could only be successfully produced by manual compaction and concreting from two sides.

By readjusting the superplasticizer quantity, the consistency could be better adjusted to the air temperature during concreting works in the second section ($t_{500} = 5.6$ s), and casting was much easier. The stripped specimen (Figure 7) showed a shortfall of the planned concrete cover in areas with several crossed grid layers (frame corner area of the web). In this case, additional spacers must be used in the final structure. Overall, the quality of the final component was satisfactory for further experimental investigation. However, it must be clearly stated that the limit of the test specimen that can still be reasonably produced was reached with the present geometry and reinforcement layout. In any case, the complexity of the reinforcement arrangement exceeds all elements manufactured and tested so far at the IMB of RWTH Aachen University in the field of non-metallic reinforcement.

Figure 7: Component test specimen after formwork removal (Graphic: IMB RWTH)

Testing and discussion of the results

The preparation of the large-scale test was under the influence of many uncertainties, since the final failure mechanism could not be predicted with certainty. Due to the potentially brittle fracture that occurs in concrete splitting, in concrete compression strut failure or in the case of fracture of the non-metallic flexural or shear reinforcement, additional safety measures were required for the personnel involved, e.g. protective walls and inclined restraints of the upper abutment of the load application (Figure 8). The critical part of the frame corner, where anchorage failure of the bar reinforcement was supposed to occur, was covered by the support blocks of the girder to minimize the potential damage of flying concrete pieces (Figure 8, yellow steel blocks).

Figure 8: Test specimen before testing (Photo: IMB RWTH)

Overall, the testing of the component worked very well. No unexpected behaviour occurred, and the measurement equipment was functional during the test. The failure was announced by pronounced flexural and shear cracking in the web, slab, and back wall (Figure 9). The final failure was a bond splitting starting from the six horizontal GFRP bars in the web area, more precisely in the compression zone of the frame corner at a test load of 162 kN. At this load, an average strain of approx. 8 ‰ was present in the uppermost of the three layers of horizontal bars, corresponding to a stress of approx. 480 N/mm² - more than the design tensile strength of this material that can be calculated ($580/1.3 = 446$ N/mm²). Interestingly, this failure was also announced: Even before the ultimate load was reached, a vertical splitting crack at the face of the web in extension of the six horizontal GFRP bars at load level 120 kN was visible due to strain decay of the strain gage applied there on the outside of the concrete. The crack was also macroscopically visible prior to failure, most recently at 150 kN, but was initially effectively bridged by the preformed CFRP profiles present there. Only when the load was further increased, the CFRP reinforcement ruptured in its bend, resulting in the loss of the confinement effect. Consequently, the crack was able to open further and completely split the web, which was accompanied by a loss of the global load-bearing capacity of the component. In the case of anchorage failure due to splitting, the influence of long-term effects (e.g. due to creep or damage to the polymer resin) is presumably less pronounced than in the case of anchorage failure due to shearing of the bar ribs. The latter is the basis for the design value of the applicable bond stress from (Schöck Bauteile GmbH, 2019), which was determined on fully confined specimens in the long-term bond test. According to EC2, Section 8.4.2 (Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V [DIN], 2011), no creep reduction is to be applied to the tensile strength of the concrete, which is the basis for calculating the anchorage length, in the context of the composite ($\alpha_{ct} = 1.0$). Against this background, the authors believe that the results of the short-term test can certainly be transferred to the design of the final bridge in terms of anchorage, or at least a comparison can be made between the experimentally determined bond strength (for splitting) and the theoretically applicable design bond strength (according to approval). In any case, the evaluation results in the requirement that the entire calculated splitting tensile force from the anchoring of the bars must be covered by confinement reinforcement. Otherwise, anchorage of the bars cannot be verified in the calculation. This means that in addition to the existing edge restraints, confinement profiles made of CFRP must be installed around the horizontal and vertical bars near their ends. Strictly speaking, the design values of the bond strength given in (Schöck Bauteile GmbH, 2019) can only be applied to restrained cross-sections or slabs with confinement effect of the bars, in which global bond splitting is effectively excluded and/or the crack widths of the opening splitting cracks are effectively limited to 0,2 mm. In the following, only the results at ultimate load level are discussed. Neither bending nor shear capacity were decisive in this short-term test on the component. However, this does not replace a design and an assessment on a theoretical basis, since the applicable strengths from long-term tests are considerably lower than the short-term strengths, especially for GFRP reinforcement, and no characteristic resistance can be derived based on the one test. However, one result of this large-scale test is that the combination of different types of reinforcement did not lead to undesirable effects (spalling, premature fracture of better-bonded reinforcement, etc.). From the crack pattern, it is

possible to draw very good conclusions about the stress distribution in the frame corner, since the reinforcement stresses achieved in the test are close to those specified in the design. It should be noted that in the design, the anchorage failure of the bar reinforcement was also decisive for the choice of the reinforcement cross-section.

a) Crack pattern after end of test b) Detail of anchorage zone with spalling
 Figure 9: Crack pattern of the specimen after end of test (Photos: IMB RWTH)

The strut-and-tie model assumed by the designer matches the observed crack pattern. This can be confirmed by the measurement results of DMS and FOS. First of all, it can be stated that the measurements of the distributed measurement with FOS fit very well to the point-measurement results of the DMS (Figure 10). The measurement was performed on two different bars (Ho1/Ho4) at the same level. The scatter of the distributed measurement is partly explained by the milled ribs of the bars, as recognized in advance on uniaxial tensile tests and simple 4-point bending tests, partly they are inherent to the FOS system. Since the measurement with the fiber takes place close to the circumference in a milled slot (depth approx. 1 mm), local strain peaks should not be equated with the average bar strain of the entire cross-section. A smoothing (trend line), as drawn for the last load level LS5 in solid black, facilitates the evaluation.

Starting from the load introduction on the left, the stress in the bars in Figure 10 initially increases only slightly and then remains almost constant. This plateau is easily explained by the haunch geometry and fits very well with the computationally predicted stresses. The steep increase of the bar stress begins well before the end of the slab, since the forces present in the planar CFRP reinforcement of the slab have to be redistributed to the bars. In the node itself, the bars then bear almost exclusively, the contribution of the monolithic slab-back wall connection is negligible because the full reinforcement cross-section (2 layers) cannot be taken around the corner in a flexurally stiff manner. Of particular interest for the assessment is the behaviour in the anchorage zone of the bars. Here, there is initially another plateau in the direct node region, followed by an approximately linear decrease in bar strain from about 8 ‰ to just over 1.7 ‰. At the end, however, the gradient becomes visibly steeper. Due to the necessary termination of the FOS, the continuous measurement ends about 3.6 cm before the end of the rod. Obviously, however, there is still a comparatively high force (about 32 kN) in the bar at this point. If the mean gradient of the strain curve were extrapolated to the end of the bar (assuming constant bond stress over the bond length), this force could not be anchored. In other words, the part of the bar anchored in the compression zone of the frame corner must provide a larger share for anchorage, equivalent to an end anchorage element. In view of the crack pattern in this area and the knowledge of the poorer anchorage in cracked concrete, this observation is plausible. If a high residual force has to be anchored at the end of the bar, this leads to concentrated splitting forces. These are superimposed with the transverse tensile forces from the flexural-compression action of the frame corner and the internal deflection forces that arise when compression stresses flow around the rebars due to their small modulus of elasticity perpendicular to the bar axis. The observed failure mechanism – bond splitting at the face with fracture of the preformed reinforcement - consequently fits very well with the strain measurements on the bar.

The preformed reinforcement was initially effective in limiting the splitting crack opening. For an effective control, however, too few fiber strands were available in the immediate anchorage zone, and with further load increase, the profiles ruptured in their bend. This results in two requirements: First, the bars should be guided as close as possible to the face of the web. Second, additional preformed reinforcement similar to helical reinforcement in tendon anchorage should encase the bars in the compression zone of the frame corner. In this way, the frame load-bearing effect remains intact even after splitting cracks occur and the overall resistance of the component can be increased once again.

Figure 10: Evaluation of the fiber optic and conventional measuring points using the example of the top horizontal bar pair (Graphic: IMB RWTH)

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In the presented project, the limits of what is currently feasible in the field of concrete components with non-metallic reinforcement were redefined to a certain extent at several points: In the complexity of the non-metallic reinforcement as a combination of bars and grids, in the reinforcement layout in the frame corner with opening moment, in the small cross-sectional dimensions in connection with a demanding geometry, and last but not least in the mixed verification concept. This was only achieved through vital cooperation, perseverance and the will of the planners, engineers, client, experts and the approval authority to create something extraordinary.

The potential savings in concrete and thus in dead weight and reduction of the CO₂ footprint in carbon concrete construction can only be achieved if resolved geometries are planned in combination with haunches and prestressing. However, with minimum concrete cover and thinned-out cross-sectional dimensions, the anchorage of the reinforcement elements can then become decisive for the global load-bearing capacity to a greater extent than in conventional reinforced concrete structures. The designer must internalize this and critically question the boundary conditions for which the characteristics specified by the manufacturer for bars, grids and preformed sections are valid. However, the construction method with non-metallic reinforcement only really makes sense if the design is consciously low-maintenance and, by omission of sealing and protective layers, a cost-efficient structure is created – calculated over the entire life cycle. In other words, steel should not only be substituted, but the design should be completely re-thought. In this project, no comparison has been made regarding Global Warming Potential (or equivalent CO₂ emissions) compared to a conventional steel-reinforced prestressed bridge. In such a comparison not only the structural components should be incorporated, but the so-called functional unit used in comparative studies should encompass also the sealing layers, and their required maintenance throughout the planned service life.

In the bridge structure described here, bar-shaped reinforcement and distributed grid-shaped reinforcement and preformed sections complement each other in a meaningful way. As already

recognized in (Bielak, 2021), it is not necessary to make a strict distinction between bar and grid. Construction with non-metallic reinforcement must be characterized by a smooth transition and the smart choice of an adapted reinforcement cross-section.

The demanding structure of the bridge over Ludwigsburger Street can only be realized at the present time by combining various forms of verification, theoretical considerations and the use of new test results: linear and nonlinear 3D FE calculations, component testing, small-specimen tests, and many years of experience of those involved with the materials used. Modern measurement techniques such as FOS and DIC support the evaluation of test results, but do not replace the necessary engineering mind-set and design by all parties involved.

The planned guideline "Concrete components with non-metallic reinforcement" of the DAfStb proposes standardized rules for planning and testing, which certainly make construction with carbon concrete much easier, but do not represent a blueprint for every case. The fundamental choice of the right structure, appropriate material and suitable verification concept for the respective purpose will therefore remain the exciting and challenging task of the designing engineers in the future.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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